

Oracle service dashboards and alerts in Grafana using Oracle Enterprise Manager Plugin

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AUTHOR:

Nourhene Jallali

National Engineering School of Tunis, TU Braunschweig

SUPERVISOR:

Miroslav Potocky

Andrzej Nowicki

CERN

PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The integration of Oracle Enterprise Manager (OEM) with Grafana aims to create dynamic and real-time dashboards and alerts for monitoring Oracle services. This project leverages the comprehensive monitoring capabilities of OEM and the powerful data visualization and alerting features of Grafana to enhance the visibility and management of Oracle service metrics. By connecting Grafana to OEM through the Oracle Enterprise Manager Plugin, key metrics are visualized, enabling administrators to monitor performance and reliability effectively.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Today, keeping track of IT systems is more important than ever. Companies rely heavily on their databases to run smoothly and perform well. Oracle databases are crucial in this setup, storing essential business data and supporting critical applications. To ensure these databases run efficiently, we need powerful tools to monitor their health, performance, and configurations.

Grafana is a popular open-source tool that helps visualize and analyze data from different sources. It's known for its flexibility and powerful features, allowing users to create custom dashboards to monitor their systems. The Oracle Enterprise Manager (OEM) plugin for Grafana is valuable, making it easy to connect Grafana to Oracle databases and pull in important metrics.

This project, supported by CERN, aims to use Grafana and the OEM plugin to build clear and useful dashboards for monitoring Oracle services. CERN, the European Organization for Nuclear Research, is renowned for its advanced research and technological innovations. By integrating Grafana with Oracle Enterprise Manager, CERN seeks to enhance its ability to monitor and manage critical database systems effectively. These dashboards will help database administrators, managers, and other users keep track of key metrics and respond quickly to any issues. Additionally, we will set up alerts to notify users of any problems, helping to maintain smooth and efficient operations.

2. PROJECT OVERVIEW

Grafana is a popular open-source tool that helps visualize and analyze data from different sources. It's known for its flexibility and powerful features, allowing users to create custom dashboards to monitor their systems. The Oracle Enterprise Manager (OEM) plugin for Grafana is a valuable tool that makes it easy to connect Grafana to Oracle databases and pull in important metrics.

This project aims to use Grafana and the OEM plugin to build clear and useful dashboards for monitoring Oracle services. These dashboards will help database administrators, managers, and other users keep track of key metrics and respond quickly to any issues. Additionally, we will set up alerts to notify users of any problems, helping to maintain smooth and efficient operations.

The figure 1 illustrates the project's architecture for monitoring Oracle databases using Grafana and the Oracle Enterprise Manager (OEM) plugin. Metric data from Oracle databases is integrated into Grafana through the OEM plugin, which generates various dashboards for service health, performance, and configuration. Grafana also features a unified alerting system that notifies users of critical issues. Alerts are configured to be sent via email or Mattermost through webhooks, ensuring that users receive timely notifications based on predefined thresholds and metrics. The entire system is designed to be flexible and customizable, allowing for adjustments to meet evolving organizational needs and ensuring that users can efficiently manage and respond to database performance and configuration challenges.

Figure 1. Project Overview

3. INSTALLATION AND CONFIGURATION

This section will describe how to install and configure Grafana and the Oracle Enterprise Manager plugin and set up the data source.

a. Install the Oracle Enterprise Manager Plugin for Grafana

You can install the Oracle Enterprise Manager App for Grafana using the Grafana command line interface (preferred) or manually.

Using the Grafana CLI

1. Navigate to `$GRAFANA_HOME/bin`
2. Install the Oracle Enterprise Manager App for Grafana, [1].
Using `--pluginUrl` option through `grafana-cli`
`./grafana-cli --pluginUrl<FULL_PATH>/oracle-emcc-app-<VERSION>.zip plugins install oracle-emcc-app`

Without the Grafana CLI

1. Navigate to the Grafana plugins directory
`cd $GRAFANA_HOME/data/plugins`
2. Extract the content of the OEM App for Grafana zip file in the Grafana plugin directory.
`cd $GRAFANA_HOME/data/plugins`
`unzip <EM App for Grafana>.zip`
3. Restart the Grafana server.
`cd $GRAFANA_HOME/bin`
`./grafana-server`

Note: The Oracle Enterprise Manager (OEM) plugin for Grafana is installed using RPM-based methods as configured by the IT-DA team at CERN. This RPM-based installation approach is managed according to their procedures and was not configured by me.

b. Enable the Oracle Enterprise Manager Plugin for Grafana

To enable the Oracle Enterprise Manager App for Grafana, simply go to the Grafana plugin settings and click the Enable button for the Oracle Enterprise Manager App. Then, make sure to adjust the settings on your Enterprise Manager site to allow Grafana to access it. To ensure optimal performance, manage data requests and API calls to prevent overloading the system.

c. Add the Oracle Enterprise Manager as a Data Source

Before creating a dashboard, you need to specify an Enterprise Manager App from which the dashboard will pull data.

To add the Oracle Enterprise Manager as a data source:

1. From the left tool bar, choose Configuration > Data Sources.
2. Click Add data source. A list of data source types is displayed.
3. Select Oracle Enterprise Manager.

Figure 2. Add Oracle Enterprise Manager as a Data Source

d. View Predefined Dashboards

The Oracle Enterprise Manager App for Grafana ships with predefined dashboards that let you visualize key operational data about Oracle services.

You can click on one of the sample dashboards below to view them. Additionally, you can create copies of these dashboards and customize them to suit your specific needs.

Note: Depending on the number of users viewing these dashboards and the selected timeframe, OEM API request limits may need to be adjusted accordingly. For detailed guidance on managing these limits, please refer to the Oracle documentation, [2].

Figure 3. Predefined Dashboards

4. RESULTS

The results section presents the integration of the selected metrics into the Oracle services dashboards and the configuration of Grafana alerts, showcasing how the key metrics are visualized and monitored for optimal performance management.

a. Metrics Identification

Out of hundreds of available metrics, 8 crucial metrics were selected based on their importance in monitoring the health and performance of Oracle services. These metrics are essential for gaining insights into the system's performance and detecting potential issues. The selected metrics include:

User metrics

Name of the Metric	Calculation	Which impact measures	User community	Collection Frequency
Latency	Latency as calculated by AWR views in DB	User perceived service performance	DB instance	Every 30 Minutes
Throughput	Throughput as calculated by AWR views in DB	User perceived service performance	DB instance	Every 30 Minutes

Management metrics

Name of the Metric	Calculation	Which impact measures	User community	Collection Frequency
Number of instances	Count of all instances	Service growth	Deployment type (RAC, Single, Cloud)	Every 24 hours
Number of schemas	Count of all schemas	Service growth	ALL	Every 24 hours
OCPU count	Sum of physical CPUs / 2 (for intel and AMD)	Licensing requirement	ALL	Every 24 hours
Feature pack usage	List of feature packs per database	Licensing requirement	Feature pack	Every 24 hours
Database status	The availability of the database	Service health	ALL	Every 5 Minutes

Here are some examples of the SQL queries used to extract relevant data from the OEM:

```
Query 1 Transform data 0
A ($oem_gf_emsite)
Query Type Non-time ser... Series Custom (Reposito...
Query SELECT NAME, DATABASE_NAME, TARGET_TYPE, CURRENTLY_USED,
SUM(DETECTED_USAGES) AS TOTAL_DETECTED_USAGES
FROM sysman.MGMT$DB_FEATUREUSAGE
GROUP BY DATABASE_NAME, CURRENTLY_USED, TARGET_TYPE, NAME;
```

```
Query 1 Transform data 0
A ($oem_gf_emsite)
Query Type Non-time ser... Series Custom (Reposito...
Query select substr(target_name,0,instr(target_name,'_',-1)-1) as target_name ,
count(distinct USERNAME) as number_schemas
from MGMT$DB_USERS
group by substr(target_name,0,instr(target_name,'_',-1)-1)
order by 1;
```

```
Query 1 Transform data 0
A ($oem_gf_emsite)
Query Type Non-time ser... Series Custom (Reposito...
Query SELECT SUM(CPU_COUNT) / 2 AS Number_of_Oracle_CPU
FROM sysman.MGMT$OS_HW_SUMMARY;
```


b. Oracle Service Dashboards

Grafana dashboards were developed to visualize these key metrics in real-time. The dashboards contain panels that display the metrics, providing a comprehensive view of Oracle's service health and performance.

Figure 4 presents the user metrics dashboard. User metrics such as throughput and latency were included due to their crucial role in performance assessment. Throughput, calculated by AWR views in the database, shows the rate of data processed by the database. It helps us understand how much data the system can handle and is visualized using stat panels. For example, the throughput of an example of a database is around 2.31GB/s. Latency, also calculated by AWR views, measures the time it takes for a request to be processed. This impacts how users experience the service and is visualized using time series graphs to show trends and spikes over time.

Figure 4. User Metrics Dashboard

Figure 5 presents the management metrics dashboard. It displays different system performance metrics:

- Number of Oracle CPU (OCPU): Shown as a gauge, with around 626 OCPU. This impacts the number of software licenses required.
- Number of Instances: Shown as a gauge, with 155 instances. This metric affects how much the service can grow by indicating how many resources are needed.
- Total Number of Schemas per Database: Shown in a table, this metric affects service health by providing insights into database complexity and usage.
- Feature Packs: Shown in a table, this panel focuses on the current used feature packs, indicating "true" if a feature pack is used and "false" if it is not. The feature packs used in each database influence the licensing requirements.

- Database Status: this is a crucial metric as it shows whether the data is available by indicating the target status (up or down). This has a significant impact on understanding the availability and reliability of the database.

Figure 5. Management Metrics Dashboard

c. Grafana Alerts

Unified alerting was set up to monitor key metrics and ensure quick responses to potential problems. Alerts in Grafana track specific thresholds and send notifications when there are issues with service or performance. This helps keep Oracle services reliable and performing well by allowing for fast action when something goes wrong.

Figure 6. Alerts Configuration

Here, we will explain how to create alerts in Grafana, set alert conditions, and configure notifications to keep track of important events and receive timely updates.

1. **Alert Rule:** We started by defining the alert rules. These rules specify the conditions under which an alert should be triggered. For example, if the latency exceeds 2s or if a database status is down.

Figure 7. Alert rules (Example of High Service Latency)

2. **Evaluation Period:** We set the evaluation period to determine how often Grafana checks the metrics against the alert rules. This could be every minute or every five minutes, depending on how critical the metric is.

Figure 8. Evaluation Period (Example High Service Latency)

The evaluation period affects the alert state in the following ways:

- **Normal:** When the metric is within the defined threshold, the alert status is OK.
- **Pending:** When the metric exceeds the threshold, the alert goes into a pending state. Grafana continues to evaluate the metric during the next evaluation periods to confirm if the condition persists.
- **Firing:** If the condition still exceeds the threshold after the pending period, the alert status changes to firing, and notifications are sent out.

For example, if the alert rule is set to trigger when latency exceeds 2 seconds, Grafana will check the latency every 1 to 5 minutes. If latency exceeds 2 seconds during a check, the alert goes to a pending state. If latency remains above 2 seconds in the next evaluation period, the alert status changes to firing, and notifications are sent out to the relevant personnel. This helps ensure timely detection and response to high latency issues, maintaining optimal performance of Oracle services.

Here I have included a screenshot (Figure 9) showing when the alert status is Normal, meaning the latency is within acceptable limits.

Figure 9. Alert state (Example High Service Latency)

3. **Notification Policy:** Next, we set up the notification policy, which determines how and when alerts are sent out. This includes setting up escalations and ensuring that alerts are only sent during specific times if necessary.

Figure 10. Notification Policies

4. **Contact Points:** Finally, we defined the contact points, which are the channels through which notifications are sent. For this project, we chose to use email and webhook as our contact points to ensure alerts are delivered promptly to the right people.
- **Email:** We created a new contact point, chose "Email" as the type, and entered the appropriate email address. We customized the message template to include all relevant information about the alert. Finally, we tested the email notification to confirm that the alerts were correctly sent out to this email address.

Figure 11. Email Configuration

When the alert state is firing, a notification will be sent to the email that we've configured. We can check the dashboard to investigate the issue and silence the alert if it's not critical. We've included an example of an alert for the latency panel.

Figure 12. Alert Notification (Email)

- **Mattermost:** To integrate Grafana alerts with Mattermost using a webhook, we first need to configure a webhook in Mattermost.

Here's how we can achieve this:

Step 1: Set Up Webhook Integration in Mattermost:

- Create a new Mattermost channel where we want to receive alerts.
- Select "Integrations" from the dropdown menu.
- Choose "Incoming Webhooks" and click "Add Incoming Webhook."
- Fill in the required details, such as the title, the channel, and the description of the webhook.
- Copy the generated webhook URL. This URL will be used in Grafana to send alerts to Mattermost.

Incoming Webhooks > Edit

Title

Specify a title, of up to 64 characters, for the webhook settings page.

Description

Describe your incoming webhook.

Channel

This is the default public or private channel that receives the webhook payloads. When setting up the webhook, you must belong to the private channel.

Lock to this channel

grafana-alerts [Edit](#) - [Delete](#)

This webhook allows Grafana to send automated notifications directly to this Mattermost channel.

URL: <https://mattermost.web.cern.ch>

Created by njallali on Friday, July 26, 2024

Figure 13. Adding Incoming Webhook

Step 2: Configure Grafana to Use the Webhook:

- In Grafana, go to the "Alerting" section and select "Contact points."
- Click on "New contact point" and choose "Slack" as the type.
- Paste the Mattermost webhook URL that we copied earlier into the URL field.
- Customize the message template to include relevant information about the alert. This ensures that the alert messages sent to Mattermost are informative and actionable.
- Test the webhook notification to confirm that alerts are correctly sent to the specified Mattermost channel.
- When the alert state is firing, we will receive a notification in the Mattermost channel that we already use.
- We have included an example of an alert for the latency panel.
- We can check the source of the alert, the panel, or the dashboard and decide if it needs to be reviewed further or silenced.

Figure 14. Configuring Webhook in Grafana

Figure 15. Alert Notification (Mattermost)

5. CONCLUSION

This project successfully integrated Oracle services with Grafana to monitor and manage system performance. We built dashboards to visualize crucial metrics like database status, throughput, and latency, which help us understand and improve system health. By setting up alerts, we ensured that any issues, such as high latency or dropped throughput, are detected quickly and addressed promptly. This monitoring setup makes our Oracle services more reliable and helps us maintain high performance, ultimately improving user experience.

6. PATHS OF FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

For future work, we suggest creating a Grafana dashboard specifically for Oracle Cloud Infrastructure to better monitor cloud resources. Adding features to show HOT/COLD tablespace files in the database could give more detailed insights into storage use. We also recommend using AI and machine learning to analyze past data and predict potential issues before they happen. This way, problems can be caught early and fixed quickly, helping to keep the system running smoothly.

7. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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